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Christian Dilemma of the Rite of *Evwe-Hun* (Waist Goat) in Urhobo Traditional Burial

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ABSTRACT

Urhobo is an ethnic nationality in Delta State, Nigeria, wherein Christianity is a religion due to the historical activities of foreign Christian missions; and present actions of indigenous Christians. Christianity in Urhobo Land impacts lives positively as many indigenes embrace the liberal religion that appears to redeem them from the ties of their known deities and divinities with so much restrictions on what, when and time to eat of, which failure to adhere to may lead to afflictions. However, the Urhobo people value some of these traditions such as marriage and burial ceremonies with their attended rites; one of which is the *Evwe-hun*, which means the killing of a waist goat to appreciate a dead parent for given birth to them. Though some Christian denominations allow their congregations who are Urhobo to cooperate with their family wishes for the observance of the rite, provided the clergy pray over it for both the family and the church to eat it, while some see it as a way of practicing religious syncretism and also worshipping the dead. However, some Christians, haven't seen the repercussion, engage in the rite of *Evwe-hun*, in spite of the messages and teachings about the implication of the rite on them and the church by their clergies. Thus, the observance of *Evwe-hun* has become a dilemma among Christians and churches in Urhobo land. The researcher applies descriptive research, and oral interview methods to investigate and discuss the dilemma of *Evwe-hun* rite among Christians and churches in Urhobo, Delta State, Nigeria. Findings indicate that many Christians hold to the rite, *Evwe-hun*, due to concerns about the repercussion of not observing the rite; and the traditional need to honour one's parents, even in death. Therefore, clergies should continue to teach against it; however, if there is no solution, such goat should be taken to the church, to appreciate the Almighty God for their parents, during their thanksgiving service in conclusion of the burial ceremony.

Keywords: *Evwe-hun*, Traditional rites, Religious practices; Urhobo.

INTRODUCTION

The Urhobo people like other people groups occupy majorly Delta Central Geo-Political Zone within Longitude 50.30 and 60.23 East, and between Latitude 60 and 50.15 North. They have boundaries with Itsekiri, the Bini, the Ijo, the Isoko, and the Ukuwani. They are the 6th largest ethnic group in Nigeria. They are found in Ethiope East, Ethiope West, Okpe, Sapele, Udu, Ughelli North, Ughelli South, Uvwie, and Warri South Local Government Areas of Delta State. According to Erhivwo (2006), some Urhobo communities are in Bayelsa, while many Urhobo communities are in Ikale District of Okitipupa, and in several other states in Nigeria and abroad. These are Urhobo in Diaspora. The Urhobo people have a unique traditional views about death, Eschatological thought, funeral or burial ceremony, funeral rites

among which is *Evwe-hun* (Waist Goat) that has become a dilemma among some Urhobo Christians. This article discussed Christian dilemma of the rite of *evwe-hun* (waist goat) in Urhobo traditional burial under the following subheadings: the advent of Christianity in Urhobo land, Urhobo traditional view of death, Urhobo eschatological thought, Urhobo traditional burial ceremony, Urhobo traditional burial rites; and the Christian dilemma of *evwe-hun*.

Advent of Christianity in Urhobo Land

Before the Coming of Christianity to Urhobo Land, the Urhobo People were practicing their traditional religion, which has a lot of taboos and death as one of the consequences of disobedience. Most adherents of the traditional religion were gripped with fear but when Christianity came as a tool for Liberation, many Urhobo people graciously embraced the new found religion. According to Erivwo (2006) that Church Missionary Society (C.M.S) came to Urhobo land through Samuel AjayiGrowther between 1841, 1854, and 1857, while Catholic Church was introduced by I. A. Ayube, an Itsekiri from Igbogidi with an Urhobo mother from Ekiugbo, Ughelli in 1916 the church was established in Ekuigbo. Some year's Later Sadjere who was baptized in December 1921 organize a Roman Catholic Church at Ovwo before other branches sprang up in Iqbogidi, Ophori in Agbarho, Oguname, Ovu, and Ewvreni. Erivwo (2006) also added that between 1917-1935, Omatsola let a Splinter group from Anglican Church in Sapele and they moved to Lagos as a body to meet I.R. Williams to seek admission into the Baptist Church and have a branch started at Sapele, which gave rise to the planting of First Baptist Church, Sapele. From the above assertion, all other denomination began to spring up either through splinting away or ambition to become General Overseers'.

When Christianity had settled down, it began to disciple its followers in her own ethics and to let go all practices believed to beat variance with the teachings of the Church. Some of those practices among Urhobo People include marrying of many wives according to the strength of the man, traditional burial rites and many more. Due to the intensive teaching and preaching by Urhobo Christians, most of the burial rites were let go or reduced to the barest minimum such as Showing of hear for the dead, preparation for second burial rite, and going to Stream to have a bath by family members, however Killing of Waist Goat (*Evwe-hun*) for the dead remains. It has become dilemma among Christians in Urhobo Land, since some individuals are for, while few others one against.

Urhobo Traditional View of Death

Death is a cessation of life and activities in this physical world. It is also seen as a transition to the spirit world, which is the final home of all. That means all born of a woman and man must surely die either at birth, infant, young, or old. In Urhobo tradition, death at old age is celebrated unlike other mentioned types of death. Traditionally, the Urhobo people view the death of a child within a month as Otsora, the Erhi of the child slipped off or it just passed by the world. The death of an infant and one who does not grow up to youth before he passes away is spoken of as Owa emo kpe emo: he departed as a child in order to become a child again.

Premature death, especially that of a youth is variously spoken of metaphorically as *ovaboghwu*: he escaped from the people's hand and expired untimely, untimely, or *ovevbirhi*: he has been violently broken in the middle of his life. There is another type of dead known as *ughwuagbagba*: quick and painful death. This is the type of death experienced by a youth as a result of rascally living. such as stealing, immorality, poisoning, suicide, and sorcery, especially within the family circle. The death of such a person is not mourned in the community. The last one is for those who are old especially as from hundred years and above, it is *okpori*, he has gone home, or *ovwoboche uyovwihwu*: he died peacefully in his house resting his head on his hands in his own bed.

Urhobo Eschological Thought

In Urhobo, *erivwi* is the final home of all, which cannot be located by the living, however according to Nabofa (2006) that the Urhobo *erivwi* is geographically "here" but separated from this visible sphere.

Hence, it is invisible to human beings. Between this sphere and *erivwi* is a gate known as Urhoro through which the dead must pass after judgment. Unless the keeping of the gate *urhiurhoro*, opens it, one would not be admitted into the land of the dead. This gate is connected with the process of self-predestination. *Urhoro* thus plays a dual role in human life: through it *erhi* must pass and have its scheme of life sealed while coming to life, and it must also pass through it to enjoy bliss with those who had gone before it, if he/she is adjudged to be worthy of it.

It is a very strong believe among Urhobo traditional people and their Philosophical thought which in most cases Pass through oral tradition by the elders to their Children and not only through that, some who belong to *Igbe* traditional worship, (is a sect of traditional religion among Urhobo people, that use it to compose a song, which says according to Ekutanure (2025) as interviewed by the researcher:

Urherorhie de-e 2x
Urhovorhie de-
Urherethie de-e
Okirhieafowo
Urherorhie de-e

It means, Urhoro has given us or open another day, therefore we should celebrate as we worship. In that case, Urhobo is seen as a divine deity, who allows humanity to witness another day. This thought Collaborated with the ideal of Nabofa that the gate (Urhoro) also connected with self-predestination not only a gate through which the dead passes to their ancestral cut. Among the Urhobo the dead are livingfor they are not cut off from their families, because they may because reveal themselves in dreams or appear to their living relatives to give instructions, warning or information, which are normally taken seriously by those who receive them. It is also in line with the Yoruba thought as opines by Opoku (1978) that dead father is still Baba Mi (my father) and dead mother Iya mi (my mother) and their obligations and functions remain the same as when they were living in the world. All their ancestors continue to be known by their titles of relationship they had borne while they were on earth. Thus, there is essentially an unbroken and uninterrupted relationship between the living and the dead. Death, therefore, is only a transition from the material world to the spirit world, the inhabitants of which maintain their links with those in the material world.

Awolalu and Dopamu (1979) also noted that there is no rigid distinction of influence between the members of the community still here on earth and those that are in the world beyond. When here on earth, they were elders of their families. Now that they have been veiled from us, they are still elders in the world of the spirits. They do not cease to interest themselves in the general welfare of their families. To maintain the link, the living relatives must give the dead person a proper burial, if not, the spirit of the deceased according to Fuller (2001) will give them sickness and other trouble, because he will not be received into the land of the Ancestors and the living must regularly remember and feed the living dead by offering sacrifices of food, drink and animals to them at the appropriate times, the above act, Mbiti (1980) reiterated that they are the mystical ties that bind the living dead to their surviving relatives, which are not strange to Urhobo traditional people. To keep ties with the dead among Urhobo people traditionally is to worship them mostly at the ancestral altar in the home of the oldest person or senior man of the family.

Urhobo Traditional Burial Ceremony

In Urhobo, apart from the death of a king or the oldest man in a large community or clan whose deaths are honored not be announced by any person, generally, the children or relatives of the deceased will inform the extended families both from paternal and maternal side with a drink called *Ese krukoko* (calling family together) with at least a thousand naira to support it before disclosing the incident to them, even though they have heard, especially those that were around when it happened. It was at this point, that family under the presiding officer of the oldest man will formerly ask to know what led to his/her death before next agenda which centered on the kind of burial, date, and place before the budget of the burial of which children will take fifty percent (50%), immediate brothers and sisters twenty five percent (25%),

half brothers and sisters twenty percent (20%) and others five percent (5%)' which must be submitted for the assurance that the said date of the burial is sure. However individual child can make his/her own additional budget for the entertainment of his/her well-wishers including canopies as it is today. On the said date, the corpse will be brought from the mortuary for lying in state whereby, family women will dance round the casket before proceeding to the grave side. In an interview, Ogheneovo (2025) states that the senior son, daughter, last born and a family representatives will throw sound on the grave three times each before it is being filled up by those that dug it. There after general entertainment, in-laws greetings if there is any before departure except children with family members in the compound for other rites to take place. The other one even though it is not common today is the second burial. The second burial takes three to seven days to complete. The procedure is similar to the former but the only difference is that a mate decorated with cloth of the disease, seven tied scarf at the entrance, a local wood casket on a bench, seven tubers of yam, a local made palm oil lamp and at the end, either the casket is destroyed or buried in a secret place. Since the actual dead have been buried.

Urhobo Traditional Burial Rites

Urhobo traditional burial rites are those items used to honor, bless, as fare well, appreciate, for peaceful co-existence and as a way of worshipping the dead. They include crying, dancing round the casket by family women singing sorrowful songs, goat for the bathing of the deceased, *evwer'inihun*, *evweoko*, procession by family members including children called *alegbe*, shaving of hair, going to a stream for a bath by family members and killing of the waist Goat, *evwe-hun*. In Urhobo when a loved one dies, it is expected that those left behind, should cry that is the reason, an individual must live a better life and die a good death. In this case an individual should impact lives positively before going to the world beyond. Crying, is hailing of the deceased that he/she had lived a good life especially that of the children. When one dies is not a lost before the ancestors. In Urhobo a person who live without a child whenever there is quarrel with one who has children would be mocked at that '*wo de ghwu, ovwomoro cha vie we kpo-o'* (that is when you die, there is no child who will share tears as you depart home). Another rite is the rite of dancing round the casket by family women as honor accorded to the deceased, it makes him/her to feel elevated among the dead. Before that, the deceased has been washed by family representatives who are entitle for a he goat as a mark to appreciate them for their bravery, and again *evwe-oko* with the seven tubers of yam is for the worship of the ancestor, its blood is spilled on the yam which are thrown on the road broken into two or more to the surprise of everyone, goat that loves eaten of yam will never taste it. It is a mystery between the living and the dead. As for the killed goat, those present that have not done the second burial of their parents will never eat it otherwise, they will equally die within one week. It is believed that such goat followed the dead person to the ancestral world for more celebrations. Again, another rite is call *alegbe* it is a street dance by the family members to show the public that they have buried their beloved one successfully. They often sing this song:

Baba KporiKoyi me she
Alagbe, Baba KporiKoyi me she
She Alagbe
e-e we rhini 2x
Alagbe.

Baba is father, it therefore means that the father, who has gone, is the one we are burring, let us celebrate, then come and watch. But if the decease is a women "Baba, will be changed to Nene" which means "mother" and the other words follow.

After returning from the street to the family compound, the rite of shaving of hair is performed except the senior son and those older than the late person. The hairs signifies money to assist the dead person on his/her journey to the world beyond. The final is the procession to a river for a bath. In that process, family members on procession will be on a single file, and must not look at their back till they get to the

family compound. This act is to wash away mourning, dirty clothes due to the burial ceremony, which mark the end of the Urhobo traditional burial. In most Urhobo traditional burials, most rites have been abandoned due to the impact of Christianity.

Evwe-hun, (Waist Goat) Rite

Among the Urhobo traditional burial rites, still persist unlike others that are gradually rolling away due to strong interaction between Christianity and Urhobo traditional burial ceremony. It appears that most Urhobo people could let go of other rites but refuse to release the killing of *Evwe-hun* as the only strong-traditional rite as culture demands. Culture as defined by Eriwo (1997), is the totality of habits, ideas, beliefs, customs, social organizations, inherited artifact. The Urhobo people inherited it from their forefathers with its repercussions of failure to perform it by the children which will lead to death and other calamities. During the burial ceremony, children of the deceased will buy a she goat and presents it to the family said Ochuko (2025) in an interview. The goat is killed a day before or after Edewor, which is a holy and resting day of Urhobo people just as Sunday is to Christians. On that day, both families of the deceased will be represented i.e, father and mother side, community or street representatives and family women. The children are to present the goat alongside with the following items (1) one carton of beer, a crate of mineral, bottle of hot, four bottles of local gin (*ogogoro*), plate of kola-nuts, four thousand or five thousand naira to be supported by all children and close relatives. The purpose is to appreciate the waist of the deceased for given birth to them. At the point of praying, in some families, says Egbekoba (2025) in an interview, the children will lay their hands on the waist of the goat before invoking the spirit of the dead for acceptance as presented by the children. After praying for the well-being of the children and the family, some individual's will be delegated to kill the goat. Before now, its blood will be spilled on the wall by the door way. However, due to the strength of Christianity in Urhobo land, its blood could be spilled in a dug pit before the preparation for the sharing formula. In the sharing formula, the children in given a leg that contain the tail, a leg for father side, waist for family women, a hand for mother side, the other hand for community or street representatives and other parts for pepper soup (*ukodo*) for all present to eat. The children expected to spray those present three times with money. In Urhobo tradition, on, those who have killed their late parents own are entitled to eat, if not such individual will die.

Christian Dilemma of *Evwe-hun* (Waist Goat)

Dilemma in a circumstance in which a choice must be made between two or more alternatives that seem equally undesirable. Is more of confusion as either to accept or not due to circumstance around it. Be as it may, Christianity is a large umbrella that covers many denominations of different opinions on traditional or cultural practices. Among different denominations in Urhobo land, Catholic members have no problem with it. It is the Reverend Father who will pray over it before killing for all to eat. Some other denominations such as African Indigenous Churches also participate. However, some denominations such as Baptist, and some Pentecostal Churches strictly refute it. Though most of their members in Urhobo land find it difficult to abandon due to fear and without knowing the implication will hide under the conviction that it should be killed for both families and church members to eat after all it is not use to worship anything. Their fear centered on the belief that the dead will waste their lives and properties should they fail to kill the goat; that is the view of Agomate (2025) in an interview. The people's disposition towards the observance of the rite is evident in the saying: '*Ekpisho-shi to boyin*', which simply means one does not attend church to that level, though parent may be Christians but *Evwe-hun* is a must to be killed.

Contrary to that notion, Odjeba (2025) in an interview opines that his parents were Jehovah Witness members and he lost his father in 1977, and mother in 1998, their waist goats were not killed and nothing happened to them because his parents did not participate in the burial rites of others wherein *evwe-hun* was observed. On that note one could say that the fear of the dead make some Christians to kill waist-goat in disguise for all to eat. The implication is that, those who still kill waist goat are practicing traditional-Christian burial, which keeps tie with the ancestors and the immediate deceased.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This article discussed the dilemma of *evwe-hun* rite in Urhobo traditional burial ceremonies among Christians in Urhobo Land, Delta State, Nigeria. *Evwe-hun* is the most dangerous rite that many Urhobo Christians find difficult to let go due to beliefs that the deceased would afflict them with all kinds of calamities including death as such, they view other Christians speaking against it as deceivers. In view of that, pastors should continually educate members on the implications, though it may take time. Secondly, they should be educated not to participate, and parents should inform their families to avoid killing of their waist goat, while he are alive. And lastly, they can use the goat to appreciate God in the church for making their parents to give birth to them as they come for thanksgiving service of the concluded burial ceremony.

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